

Infrastructure for Systems Biology Europe

Work Package 4: Data Generation Centres

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Report on global standards, methods and training procedures

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Overview

Systems Biology is at the current frontier of life sciences, representing a highly interdisciplinary approach for understanding biological complexity in health and disease. In the last decades it has become clear that all life sciences relate to systems. The focus of medicine today is the systematic and systemic treatment of all multifactorial diseases, as compared to traditional single molecule targeted approaches. ISBE, the European Systems Biology Infrastructure, will be capable of supporting technology transfer as well as of translating scientific and medical discoveries into medical and other applied concepts that will improve both our basic understanding of life and Medicine and enhance the economic potential of Europe. Biological research projects involve collaborations between groups in various institutions, each with specific expertise and/or facilities working synergistically. Building on such experiences gained by European research consortia in systems biology, ISBE as an integrated research infrastructure, will exploit existing synergies and will create new opportunities for efficient research coordination and collaboration. ISBE will also make available cutting-edge technologies in experimental and computational systems analysis to the wider community of European life scientists. Centres specializing in specific experimental and/or computational technologies will combine in a variety of operational clusters to create the backbone of the infrastructure. These Centres will contribute to ISBE not just through specific projects, but also through the training of researchers - and by acting as hubs for stimulating further technology development. Additionally, the ISBE Centres-Data Generation-Stewardship-Modelling, will catalyze the broader integration of the quantitative sciences of physics, mathematics and engineering with biology by providing a unique environment where scientists from all these disciplines meet, work together and educate/train each other.

ISBE is envisaged as an infrastructure where clusters of research groups from institutions/Centres will focus their various and specialized expertise on discovery-directed and hypothesis-driven research, and/or by contributing to the development of underpinning technologies. Some clusters will focus on distinct conceptual aspects of biology - such as model organisms, model cell populations, diseases, biotechnology, ecology etc; others will have a central focus on the development and application of new technologies. The combined expertise and facilities of ISBE will serve the European Research Area by functioning as the entity for addressing important scientific problems, by disseminating technologies and by providing open and active access to data, software and experimental and modeling facilities (e.g. to the extent of enabling external researchers to perform experiments in a relevant cluster either directly or real-time-through-web). Although ISBE institutions/Centres will have complementary activities, each will typically support the following: *de novo* data generation, data extraction from all pre-existing sources, data management and curation, data analysis, model extraction from literature, *de novo* model generation and validation, visualisation and modelling, dynamic interaction of models and data, model-driven experimental design, and training. Importantly, ISBE will take a leading role in exploring, developing and establishing the necessary standards for experimentation and modelling in systems biology, critical for ensuring the delivery of reliable and consistent data across the infrastructure. A key deliverable of ISBE will be to bring focus to these disparate efforts by identifying, structuring and supporting large-scale research projects on major areas of urgent need in medicine, the biosciences and the economy - for example, human physiology and ageing, complex diseases, bioenergy and bio-manufacturing. Finally, such a focused European infrastructure will offer a single point of contact for access to a network of best practice in Systems Biology, unique in the world, stimulating contacts with non-EU consortia from academia, industry and regulatory agencies across the globe, as well as other related infrastructures and programs within the EU.

Data Generation Centres: Technological and Training issues

The goal is to develop a comprehensive plan based on the survey performed on task 4.1 to identify which of the existing infrastructures are capable of providing access to high throughput technologies and training to the acquirement of systems biology-grade data. In parallel, the gaps in the available infrastructure and the needs for building new centres will be defined. Furthermore, the level of commitment of the existing and new infrastructures to the future of ISBE will be defined.

The conceptual challenge for such a plan for the distributed Data Generation Centres is based on:

- *technological issues*: currently, there exist technological deficits especially in single-cell –omics technologies, in mathematics, computation and other experimentation. There are continuing challenges in applying mathematics to the complexity of living systems. Growing volumes of data from diverse high-throughput experiments provide unprecedented challenges for computational biologists, but also challenges in data storage, analysis, archiving and visualization. Experimentally, there is a demand for high-throughput and other technologies that will help populate quantitative models. Further improvements in measurements at all scales are needed. It is particularly important to sample living systems dynamically, at multiple scales, if realistic models are to be constructed. The systems biology Centres are encouraged to develop innovative approaches to address these and other technological challenges.
- *Training, Outreach and Organizational Challenges*. Building cohesive multi-disciplinary research teams by integrating expertise across traditional disciplinary boundaries is not a simple undertaking. There is a continuing need to disseminate knowledge widely through outreach activities to the research community through appropriate conferences, personnel exchanges, and sharing of resources. Importantly, the emergence of a new science demands an

adequate, diverse workforce of appropriately trained scientists. The future leaders of systems biology research will be knowledgeable and skilled in both experiment and computation. Innovation in research training therefore, is a significant task of the Data Generation Centres.

Education is recognized as a key component in the success of any systems biology program. It is recognized that a balance needs to be established between the need to become interdisciplinary and the requirement of having extensive specialist knowledge in particular areas. Collaborative research is a key method of combining the skills necessary for large projects, while ensuring that there is proper communication and understanding among all relevant participants. In the development of the training program for systems biology, we should adapt the education of undergraduates and graduate students so as to integrate big, cross-disciplinary science and small science.

ISBE Data Generation Centres (DGCs) will build a portfolio of training and education components in the experimentation and application of life sciences technologies. DGCs will setup and maintain an education and training program with two explicit goals: (i) introducing DTL technologies, data processing and analysis methods to inexperienced users, and (ii) offer advanced topical courses dealing with specific aspects of life science technologies, data stewardship and data integration. The training program will build on and expand the collective training efforts of the ISBE founders and it aims at PhD students and postdocs, as well as any other scientist who wishes to get insights into key technologies. Web-based tutor-supervised courses, where trainees could follow at their own leisure the program would be efficient as a first introduction into novel technologies. Furthermore, one day courses-tutorials and up to one week in-depth courses, often combining theoretical and hands-on experience will significantly enhance education and training in systems biology-related technologies.

The large amount of data produced by biological research projects grows at a fast rate.

With the exponential growth of the produced experimental data in all areas of modern biosciences, data management techniques are becoming more and more necessary to enable efficient and reproducible usage of these data. This encompasses the acquisition, cleansing, administration, curation, storage, retrieval and analysis of these data in a reasonable and easy to handle way for the working researcher. The incorporation of metadata – data about data - is of great importance. In systems biology the integration of data from heterogeneous data sources is a further great challenge. It is clear that there is an urgent need for defining standard data formats for storage, retrieval and exchange of experimental data to allow integrated data analysis procedures and methods to extract as much as possible information from the existing and coming amounts of data and to allow the generation of new information from them. It can be expected that in future with the rise of personalized medicine data management solutions are becoming extremely important also in the management of clinical data to support clinical decision support systems.

The Data Management Association (DAMA) defines data management as “... the development, execution and supervision of plans, policies, programs and practices that control, protect, deliver and enhance the value of data and information assets”. Typical topics in data as well as in metadata management are the database architecture and administration, data modelling, data mining, data analysis and integration, data quality assurance and data security.

Global standards, harmonizations and training protocols

Standard operating procedures or SOPs are written step-by-step procedures that quality control (QC), quality assurance (QA), and production units use in order to assure the accuracy and precision of the quantitative experimental results and materials that they generate and are provided to support other activities such as Research and Development (R&D), manufacturing, etc. SOPs are generally used in support of experimental research whenever there is a need to document the handling of samples,

the methods used in their analysis, and the quality of the results generated in the analysis of these samples. SOPs are used by the governmental agencies, private industry, and academic laboratories by scientists and engineers from all disciplines of science, technology and engineering. Examples of their use include the development of diagnostic/prognostic procedures, production of therapeutics, forensic analysis where they are used to establish the chain of custody of evidence and in private biotechnology industry where they are often used to validate new methods of bioanalysis, to name a few.

Key technologies, like for example genomics, proteomics, various types of analyses etc. that are constantly used by several groups have to be optimized in order to establish the necessary SOPs to ensure reproducibility not only in the acquirement of the data but also for their analyses. Thus, standards are needed to be established including those for data collection from various types of experiments, data storage in databases, 'model bases' and analysis consistent with modelling requirements. Standards need to be dynamically evolve to match the parallel advances in systems biology technologies. Based on a survey of existing and planned large-scale facilities, the development of a comprehensive plan for harmonising the existing hardware resources and developing an integrated infrastructure catering to the needs for large-scale data storage and efficient access in cooperation with other ISBE WPs is needed. The data collected from the wide ISBE survey, web search etc, serve to identify the SOPs and the best practices between research groups and proceed to their harmonization and implementation by the DGCs. Several standards are already successfully implemented and the awareness of the need for standardisation is widespread.

Impact of establishing standards

The data in systems biology projects can be obtained from many sources, using a broad variety of methods. In order to construct computer models, the data must be structured, combined and integrated. The successful application of systems biology tools relies greatly, therefore, on the standardisation of the formats and associated metadata descriptions. It is essential to uniformly format and semantically interlink

research assets that are related to each other, for instance within large multinational coordinated projects.

On a broader scale, standards in research assets allow for discovery, exchange, analysis, integration and re-usage between research labs, institutes and industry, and provide users with models that are interoperable on a number of analysis platforms. By enabling the re-use of research assets, research is made considerably more efficient and economical.

ISBE will actively promote and support the development of standards, software and algorithms that support modelling analysis within the European systems biology community, working with all stakeholders to maximise uptake. The provision of these resources will make routine building and analysis of models accessible by a wider section of the community. Centralised resources for making algorithms and software will allow users to generate standard operating procedures (SOPs) for their modelling analysis that ensure reproducibility, and provenance of their results.

The definition of parameters that have to be documented for each data point greatly facilitates the assessment of the quality of data. Additionally, standardized documentation of mathematical models is also required. The standardization process needs to be scalable to also include clinical data, since this data is often incomplete and provides more qualitative information but is extremely valuable. These efforts will be essential to establish reliable prior knowledge, which is the basis to address important questions and help to implement the framework of Systems Biology and Medicine.

Data Quality Standards

An essential prerequisite of modern life sciences is the high quality of the research data. This can only be achieved reliably and efficiently if these are generated according to standards and Standard Operating Procedures (SOPs). Standardization and quality management therefore becomes an important driver in life sciences. Standards are also essential for industrial application assuring that data become accessible, shareable and comparable along the value chain. Recently, several initiatives and individual institutions have begun the development and implementation of standards in the life sciences. Currently, however, these efforts remain fragmented and largely disconnected.

ISBE, in collaboration with other ESFRI projects, is in the process of identifying, determining and implementing the best integrated practice guidelines and stringent standards to prepare a report with recommendations for the implementation of standards to be followed by the ISBE data generation Centres. This initiative will harmonize high throughput data generation procedures not only between different institutes but also between different researchers in the same Institute.

“A standard ... is a publication that provides rules, guidelines or characteristics for activities or their results, for common and repeated use. Standards are created by bringing together all interested parties including manufacturers, users, consumers and regulators of a particular material, product, process or service. Everyone benefits from standardization through increased product safety and quality as well as lower transaction costs and prices.” ...“European Standards are a key component of the Single European Market. Although rather technical and often unknown to the public and media, they represent one of the most important issues for businesses. Standards are actually crucial in facilitating trade and hence have high visibility among manufacturers inside and outside of Europe. A standard represents a model specification, a technical solution against which a market can trade. In essence, European Standards relate to products, services or systems. Today, however, standards are no longer created solely for technical reasons but have also become platforms to enable greater social inclusiveness and engagement with technology, as well as convergence and

interoperability within growing markets across industries"... (source: <http://www.cen.eu/>)

As systems biology is gaining increasing importance in basic bio (medical) research, a number of significant and extensive research networks have been established in recent years, involving both, academic and industrial partners. The support - and the subsequent development - of these networks is essential for Europe to allow the establishment of a internationally competitive research area. Even in cases of industrial research activities (particularly in the pharmaceutical sector), systems biology plays an increasingly important role. Unfortunately, the scientific communities and European networks are currently working largely independently from each other and an efficient exchange of data is often not possible because of the lack of standards and harmonization or hindered. Thus, many experiments need to be repeated before their use in other experimental settings, requiring a great deal of time, effort and resources of all players involved. This current situation highlights the need and high demand for standards in the life sciences, thus justifying the need for the Data Generation Centres. Currently, there are more than 30 guidelines in the area of biomedical data collection and use, including among others MIAME (Minimum Information About a Microarray Experiment), MIAPE (Minimum Information About a Proteomics Experiment), STREND (Standards for Reporting Enzymology Data), and CIMR (Core Information for metabolomics Reporting). Of equal importance is the continuing day-to-day activity in the implementation of regulation/standards in data generation. Without the development of standards and their implementation in routine processes, an efficient research and exploitation of the results obtained will not be possible. Because data generation and application are closely linked, they take a key role and are key drivers for the development of standards and Standard Operating Procedures (SOPs) within biological R&D and beyond.

Although a large number of different initiatives and standards exist, they are often not compatible. Due to the rapidly growing complexity of systems biology research

exchange and collaboration between different communities are of high importance. Standardization initiatives need to be coordinated and to be compelled about the limits of each specialized area to be able to generate useful results. Currently, even by the International Organization for Standardization (ISO) the need for a comprehensive agreement on standards in the life sciences, particularly in biotechnology and related fields, is seen. The analysis and classification of existing (or under development) community standards in the field of systems biology and computational modeling (and beyond); development of a common understanding/definition of the subject matter is still needed.

Training and best practice between ISBE DGC partners.

In contrast to the present practice of educating scientists in the classical disciplines, the Systems Biology approach requires new thinking across scientific borders. New interdisciplinary BSc, MSc and PhD teaching and training programs should be implemented as a matter of urgency to address this issue (see WP 10). In this respect, an open debate with responsible European stakeholders and higher education institutions (e.g. universities) should be initiated.

The overall goal is to provide advanced training to researchers in systems biology. Systems biology aims at the determination and understanding of the properties / phenotypes that emerge through the interaction of biomolecules, genes, cells and tissues. Those properties cannot be predicted from those of the individual biomolecules. Systems biology uses a combination of experimental and mathematical approaches to achieve a deeper understanding of the function and operation of pathways, cells, organs and entire organisms.

This interdisciplinary approach to research field requires a generation of scientists trained in experimental and mathematical / computational biology, i.e. the so-called new biologists. Such scientists should ideally be able to both perform experiments and generate mathematical models related to their research question, or at least they

should understand how to combine modelling and experimentation. DGCs will undertake the task to train and educate young scientists in this new way of doing science and most importantly in the design of experiments to answer important biological questions.